

THE ROLE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL MODELING SKILLS IN 9TH GRADE STUDENTS

Gardashova Z.

*Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, doktorant,
teacher of the Department of Mathematics and its Teaching Technology,
Faculty of Mathematics, Baku*

Abstract

The digitalization of modern education makes the integration of mathematical modeling with informatics relevant in the teaching of algebra in the 9th grade. The purpose of the study is to determine the methodological role of informatics in the formation of mathematical modeling skills in students and to substantiate the advantages of the integrative teaching approach. The essence and stages of mathematical modeling are explained in the content of the article, and the relationship of algebraic sequences with informatics structures is analyzed. The study applies a methodological analysis based on comparative analysis, modeling, and the use of digital learning environments.

The results show that the algorithmic approaches of informatics and the principles of data structuring have a significant impact on students' deeper assimilation of mathematical concepts, strengthening of analytical thinking, and the development of the ability to express real situations with mathematical models.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, computer science integration, algebra teaching, algorithmic thinking, numerical sequences, digital learning.

Introduction

In the modern era, the digitalization of education puts forward new requirements for the teaching of mathematics, especially algebra. The rapid development of digital technologies makes it necessary to form students' information processing, algorithmic thinking, analytical analysis, and modeling skills. The study of algebra topics in the 9th-grade, especially the mastery of concepts such as functions, equations, and numerical sequences, requires students to think logically and build mathematical models of real situations. The integration of this process with the subject of computer science allows for a more efficient, visual, and application-oriented understanding of mathematical modeling. In this regard, the role of computer science in the development of mathematical modeling skills is currently one of the most relevant directions in the pedagogical field.

The purpose of the study is to determine the methodological potential of computer science and digital tools in the formation of mathematical modeling skills in 9th-grade students and to substantiate the integrative teaching approach. To achieve this goal, the concept of mathematical modeling, its stages, and didactic features are analyzed, as well as the logical, algorithmic, and visual connections between computer science and algebra are investigated.

Comparative analysis, literature review, modeling, and methodological analysis based on the application of collaborative learning approaches and digital programs (Graph, GeoGebra, Python, etc.) are used as research methods. These methods create conditions for evaluating new learning opportunities arising at the intersection of mathematical and computer science thinking.

The essence, stages, and application features of mathematical modeling in teaching

Mathematical modeling is one of the main components of modern mathematics education and is characterized by expressing real-life processes and phenomena in mathematical language and analyzing them on a simplified model (Blum et al., 2007). This process not only teaches students to master mathematical

knowledge but also teaches them to identify relationships between phenomena, predict outcomes, and evaluate the interaction of various variables (NCTM, 2000). In particular, modeling skills at the 9th grade level provide a deep understanding of algebraic topics and have a significant impact on the structuring of the student's mathematical thinking (OECD, 2019).

The mathematical modeling process consists of several sequential stages, and these stages systematically develop the student's ability to conduct independent analysis (Stillman & Brown, 2012):

1. Understanding the problem. At this stage, the student understands the essence of the presented real situation, accurately analyzes the problem, and determines its purpose and limitations. A correct understanding of the essence of the problem directly determines the quality of the mathematical model (Kaiser & Sriraman, 2006).

2. Building a mathematical model. The selection of features, variables, and parameters, and the determination of functional or logical relationships between them, form the basis of this stage. Equations, functions, graphs, sequences, and sometimes algorithmic structures are used in building the model (Blum et al., 2007). Grade 9 algebra topics create wide application opportunities at this stage.

3. Model solution. At this stage, operations are performed on the mathematical model built, equations are solved, functions are analyzed, and results are obtained. This process can be carried out using both symbolic, graphical, and informatics approaches (for example, using Python or Graph programs) (Yerushalmy, 2006).

4. Interpretation of results. The obtained mathematical results are compared with the real situation, their meaning is interpreted, and their accuracy is checked. At this stage, students evaluate the correspondence between the "mathematical result" and the "real result" and determine the adequacy of the model (English, 2006).

The didactic properties of mathematical modeling make it one of the most effective teaching strategies in

mathematics teaching. Modeling develops students' critical, analytical, and creative thinking, creates conditions for the formation of an active learning environment, and also allows for the establishment of connections between different fields of knowledge (Kaiser & Sriraman, 2006). Students' modeling skills strengthen both their mathematical logic and the problem-solving and decision-making competencies required in their future activities.

This process is of particular importance at the 9th-grade level. At this stage, students learn systems of equations, quadratic functions, numerical sequences, and other important algebraic concepts. The application of these concepts within the framework of mathematical modeling teaches students to build a bridge between real life and mathematical theory, formalize situations, and make decisions based on mathematical results (Stillman & Brown, 2012). Thus, modeling both provides a functional application of mathematical knowledge and creates a basis for natural integration with computer science (OECD, 2019).

The role of informatics in the development of mathematical modeling skills

In the modern educational environment, informatics plays a key role in the formation of students' skills in algorithmic thinking, logical sequence, information structuring, and process modeling (Grover & Pea, 2013). These skills directly affect the more systematic and deep mastery of all stages of mathematical modeling. Informatics allows students to create digital representations of abstract mathematical objects and test models in various software environments, which makes the teaching of algebraic topics more visual and application-oriented.

The impact of informatics on mathematical modeling is primarily related to the formation of algorithmic thinking. The algorithmic approach facilitates the identification of variables, the definition of relationships, and the step-by-step structuring of the solution when building a mathematical model (Wing, 2006). In the 9th grade, topics such as equations, functions, and sequences are fully consistent with the algorithmic description and allow the student to understand the sequential logic of a mathematical problem.

The second important aspect is visualization capabilities. In the computer science environment, graphic representations, dynamic models, simulations, and interactive presentations more clearly show the structure of a mathematical model. For example, various studies have proven that graphic models built using programs such as Graph and GeoGebra strengthen mathematical thinking (Hohenwarter & Jones, 2007). This approach provides a visual perception of the solution of equations, the properties of functions, and the interaction of variables.

The third direction is related to conducting digital experiments. By changing the values of various variables in programming environments, the dynamism of the model results is observed. Such experiments allow students to discover mathematical regularities, put forward hypotheses, and test them (Grover & Pea, 2013). As a result, the student more easily understands how to express real situations in mathematical language and conduct analysis using the model.

In addition, informatics also develops students' ability to structure and process information, which is important for all stages of mathematical modeling. Activities such as sorting data into types, determining the relationship between variables, and interpreting results are central components of both informatics and mathematics.

Consequently, integration with informatics has a multifaceted impact on the development of mathematical modeling skills: it systematizes mathematical thinking, facilitates the construction and understanding of models, makes teaching more interactive and application-oriented, and strengthens students' analytical and decision-making skills. In particular, at the IX grade level, this integration creates an important methodological potential for the development of both mathematical and digital literacy of students.

Linking numerical sequences with informatics models

In the 9th-grade "Mathematics" textbook, the topic of numerical sequences is built on basic concepts such as numerical series, geometric series, their n th term, and the sum of the first n terms (Gahramanova, Karimov & Huseynov, 2019). These topics are fully consistent with the algorithmic structures of informatics in terms of the definition of a sequence, that is, the connection of each term with a previous term or several previous terms based on a certain regularity. It is this consistency that justifies the connection of sequences with informatics models both methodologically and in terms of content.

The basic algorithmic structures used in computer science lessons - the concept of a variable, the repetition (cycle) operator, the conditional operator, and the recursive representation - allow us to model the mathematical structure of sequences. For example, the recurrent definition for a numerical sequence $a_n = a_{n-1} + d$ is naturally realized in computer science with the cycle operator. In this regard, the sequence can be presented to the student both as a mathematical equation and as an algorithm.

Mathematical description:

$$a_1 = 5, \quad a_n = a_{n-1} + 3$$

Algorithmic description (Python pseudo-code):

```

go
a = 5
for i in range(1, N+1):
    print(i, a)
    a = a + 3

```

Introducing this parallelism helps students develop two important skills:

first, structuring the order in which a sequence is constructed; second, understanding the dynamic relationship between variables (Cormen et al., 2009).

Let's look at an example with both a mathematical and an algorithmic description based on the formula $a_n = a_1 + (n-1)d$ for the n -th term of a numerical series.

Mathematical description.

Example: If the sequence contains $a_1 = 4$, $d = 3$, find a_{10} .

$$a_{10} = a_1 + (10 - 1)d$$

Solution: $a_{10} = 4 + 9 \cdot 3$

$$a_{10} = 4 + 27 = 31$$

Answer: $a_{10} = 31$.

Let's write an algorithmic description for the given example. Goal: To calculate the 10th term of the sequence, starting from the fourth term.

```
python
a = 4
d = 3

for i in range(2, 11):
    a = a + d

print(a)
```

Result: output: 31.

Geometric sequences are modeled in a similar way; the recurrent definition for a geometric sequence is $a_n = a_{n-1} \cdot q$ which is implemented in programming by looping and multiplying.

Students can observe the rate of increase/decrease of a sequence by trying different values of the q factor in Python, Scratch, or block-based environments, which reinforces mathematical concepts visually and empirically (Hohenwarter & Jones, 2007).

In addition, the principles of computer science data structuring - storing variables, creating lists, indexing sequential elements allows for the representation of a numerical sequence as a "set of terms." This approach allows for the solution of tasks set in the textbook (calculating the limit, the sum of the first n terms, etc.) together with computer science models and teaches the student to interpret both mathematical and practical results (Gahramanova, Karimov & Huseynov, 2020).

Thus, the integrated teaching of numerical sequences between mathematics and computer science allows students to master the process of constructing, changing, and analyzing sequences in a more clear, visual, and technologically based way; this connection makes a significant contribution to the development of both mathematical modeling and algorithmic thinking skills (Grover & Pea, 2013; Cormen et al., 2009; Gahramanova, Karimov & Huseynov, 2020).

Numerical sequences (and mathematical models in general) are very important not only for numerical or symbolic analysis, but also for the formation of algorithmic thinking in computer science and programming. The key point here is the interaction of mathematical representation and algorithmic representation.

1. Mathematical representation: The n th term or sum of a numerical sequence is expressed as a formula. For example, $a_n = a_1 + (n - 1)d$. This shows the regularity of the sequence.

2. Algorithmic representation: The same sequence can be calculated and automated using a programming language. For example, with Python:

```
python

a1 = 2
d = 3
n = 10
an = a1 + (n-1)*d
print("10-cu üzv:", an)
```

This teaches the student or programmer to calculate, analyze, and visualize sequences.

Algorithmic representation of numerical sequences and mathematical models through informatics develops logical thinking, problem-solving and decision-making skills in students, and also allows for the practical application of mathematical knowledge in real-life and social situations.

- **Automation of complex problems:** A person can quickly calculate large sequences and sums that a person would have to calculate manually through a program.

- **Development of analytical thinking:** Converting a mathematical formula into algorithmic steps develops the student's logical thinking and planning skills.

- **Life applications:** Sequences are implemented algorithmically in financial calculations (for example, monthly payments, interest calculations), physics, and statistical models.

- **Connection with informatics:** Mathematical model \rightarrow algorithmic model \rightarrow programming \rightarrow analysis of results. This chain strengthens the integrative approach in teaching.

That is, the algorithmic description of numerical sequences is not only for programming, but also allows the student to apply mathematical thinking to the practical world.

The role of informatics in the development of mathematical modeling skills in students is indispensable. For example, students can calculate their monthly savings plan, water or electricity consumption through numerical sequences and functions using Python or other programs. This teaches not only theoretical calculations, but also algorithmic analysis and visual display of results. Such an approach strengthens students' logical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. As a result, mathematical education integrated with informatics turns students into individuals who think independently and make decisions based on mathematical grounds in the economic, environmental, and social situations they encounter in real life.

Conclusion

The role of informatics in the development of mathematical modeling skills in grade IX is indispensable. Through informatics, students gain the ability to solve mathematical problems not only at the theoretical level, but also at the algorithmic and practical level. Programming environments and algorithmic analysis tools allow students to visually demonstrate complex sequences, functions, and algebraic structures, analyze

them, and predict results. This process also accelerates the formation of logical thinking, planning, and problem-solving skills. As a result, mathematical education integrated with informatics creates conditions for the development of functional skills in students in both mathematical and computer science, turning them into individuals who can think independently and make decisions in real-life and social situations.

Suggestions

The integration of mathematics and computer science subjects should be carried out systematically. Especially in the 9th grade, algebraic topics — functions, equations, and numerical sequences - should be taught in parallel with the algorithmic structures of computer science, and students should be shown the general logical connections of both subjects.

Digital tasks should be increased to develop mathematical modeling skills. Students should be given the opportunity to build a mathematical model of real-life situations and describe it algorithmically, and practical activities on data processing, working with variables, and generating sequences should be expanded.

The use of interactive and visual environments in teaching algebraic subjects should be strengthened. Simple programming environments that demonstrate graphics, conditional, and periodic structures should be included in the teaching process, and students should master abstract concepts through visual models.

Joint methodological training should be organized for teachers. Joint seminars, open lessons and exchange of experience of mathematics and computer science teachers would help to form a unified approach to integrative teaching.

Measurement tools should be developed that assess students' mathematical and algorithmic thinking. Assessment should be based not only on the result, but also on the skills of building models, analyzing problems, designing algorithms, and interpreting results.

More emphasis should be placed on modeling real-life problems. Data analysis on energy consumption, budget planning, production growth, environmental indicators, and other socio-economic processes strengthens the development of both mathematical and informatics skills.

References

1. Blum, W., Galbraith, P.L., Henn, H.-W., & Niss, M. (2007). *Modelling and applications in mathematics education: The 14th ICMI Study*. Springer.
2. English, L.D. (2006). Mathematical modeling in the primary school: Children's construction of a consumer guide. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 63(3), 303 - 323.
3. Kaiser, G., & Sriraman, B. (2006). A global survey of international perspectives on modelling in mathematics education. *ZDM*, 38(3), 302 - 310.
4. NCTM. (2000). *Principles and Standards for School Mathematics*. National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
5. OECD. (2019). *PISA 2021. Mathematics Framework*. OECD Publishing.
6. Stillman, G.A., & Brown, J.P. (2012). Mathematical modelling in the secondary school curriculum. In G. A. Stillman et al. (Eds.), *Teaching mathematical modelling: Connecting to research and practice* (pp. 89–98). Springer.
7. Yerushalmy, M. (2006). Slower algebra students meet faster tools: Solving algebraic problems with technology. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 25(1), 75-91.
8. Grover, S., & Pea, R. (2013). Computational thinking in K-12: A review of the state of the field. *Educational Researcher*, 42(1), 38-43. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X12463051>
9. Hohenwarter, M., & Jones, K. (2007). Ways of linking geometry and algebra: The case of GeoGebra. *Proceedings of the British Society for Research into Learning Mathematics*, 27(3), 126-131.
10. Gahramanova, N., Karimov, M., & Huseynov, I. (2020). *Mathematics-9. Textbook for the 9th grade of secondary schools*. Radius.
11. Cormen, T.H., Leiserson, C.E., Rivest, R.L., & Stein, C. (2009). *Introduction to Algorithms* (3rd ed.). MIT Press.
12. Wing, J. M. (2006). Computational thinking. *Communications of the ACM*, 49(3), 33-35. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1118178.1118215>